

AETIOLOGY OF VENTILATOR-ASSOCIATED PNEUMONIA (VAP) IN PATIENTS HAVING CANDIDA COLONIZATION IN ENDOTRACHEAL ASPIRATE

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ABSTRACT

Background and Aims: Ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) is a severe complication in intensive care unit (ICU) patients requiring prolonged mechanical ventilation. While traditionally associated with bacterial pathogens, fungal colonization, particularly by *Candida* species, has emerged as an area of interest. This study investigates the aetiology of VAP in patients with *Candida* colonization detected in endotracheal aspirates. The aim is to assess the prevalence of *Candida* spp., their role in VAP pathogenesis, and whether they necessitate specific therapeutic interventions or act as predictive markers for bacterial VAP.

Methods: This prospective observational study was conducted in the ICU of Heritage Institute of Medical Sciences, Varanasi, after ethical clearance (HIMS/IEC/127/2022). Patients aged 18 years or older on mechanical ventilation for over 48 hours were included, while those on antifungal treatment, pregnant women, and

those with positive cultures at intubation were excluded. Endotracheal aspirates were analyzed for fungal and bacterial cultures using the VITEK®2 system. Data were processed using SPSS version 25, with results expressed as mean \pm SD, median, and 95% confidence intervals. A p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: The mean age of participants was 48.28 ± 22.41 years, with males constituting 61.25%. *Candida albicans* was the most prevalent fungal isolate (63.3%), followed by *Candida tropicalis*. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (21.57%) and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (9.16%) were the leading bacterial pathogens. VAP culture positivity was observed in 34.17% of cases, with significant associations between *Candida* colonization and prolonged ventilation.

Conclusion: *Candida* spp., particularly *Candida albicans*, play a critical role in VAP pathogenesis, often co-existing with bacterial pathogens like *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. These findings highlight the need for enhanced diagnostic strategies and tailored therapeutic protocols targeting fungal and bacterial co-pathogens.

Keywords: Ventilator-associated pneumonia; *Candida albicans*; Endotracheal aspirates; ICU infections; Antimicrobial stewardship

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Introduction

Ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) remains a critical concern in intensive care units (ICUs), particularly among patients requiring prolonged mechanical ventilation. Defined as a lung infection that develops after 48 hours of invasive ventilation, VAP is a significant cause of morbidity and mortality among critically ill patients.[1] Despite advancements in microbiological diagnostics and therapeutic strategies, challenges persist in understanding its epidemiology, pathophysiology, and optimal management. VAP not only complicates patient outcomes by prolonging ventilator dependence but also extends hospital stays and imposes a substantial financial burden, with attributable costs estimated to exceed \$40,000 per patient in the United States.[2]

Traditionally, VAP has been associated with bacterial pathogens, and current preventive measures—such as oral hygiene with chlorhexidine, beta-lactam antibiotics, and probiotic administration—target bacterial colonization and infection. However, fungal colonization, particularly by *Candida* species, is an emerging area of interest. *Candida*, often regarded as a commensal organism in the respiratory tract, frequently colonizes the airways of mechanically ventilated patients. While this colonization is generally considered non-pathogenic, emerging evidence suggests that it may alter the respiratory microbiota and increase the risk of secondary bacterial infections, potentially predisposing patients to VAP.[3,4]

This study explores the aetiology of VAP in patients with *Candida* colonization detected in endotracheal aspirates. By investigating the prevalence and role of *Candida* in these cases, the research aims to clarify whether fungal colonization contributes to the pathogenesis of VAP or merely serves as an incidental finding. Additionally, the study seeks to evaluate whether the presence of *Candida* necessitates specific therapeutic considerations or acts as a predictive marker for bacterial VAP.

Understanding the interplay between Candida colonization and VAP is essential to refining diagnostic approaches and treatment strategies. This study intends to bridge existing gaps in knowledge, providing critical insights into the multifaceted nature of VAP and its management in critically ill patients.

Material and Methods

Study Design and Setting

This prospective observational study was conducted in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) under the Department of Anesthesia at Heritage Institute of Medical Sciences (HIMS), Varanasi. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee (HIMS/IEC/127/2022, dated 22/11/2022). Written informed consent was obtained from the patients or their legally authorized representatives before enrollment.

Study Population

The study included all patients admitted to the ICU and on mechanical ventilation for more than 48 hours. Endotracheal aspirate (ETA) samples were routinely collected and analyzed in the Microbiological Laboratory of HIMS.

Sample Selection

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients on mechanical ventilation for over 48 hours.
- Patients aged 18 years or older.
- Patients or their legally authorized representatives who provided informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients already receiving antifungal treatment.
- Pregnant females.
- Patients with positive ETA cultures at the time of intubation.

Sample Size Calculation

The sample size was calculated based on a Candida colonization prevalence of 19.54%, with a 95% confidence level and a 5% allowable error. Using the formula: $N = Z^2 \times P \times Q / E^2$

- $Z = 1.96$ ($Z = 1.96$ (95% confidence level))
- $P = 19.54$ ($P = 19.54$ (prevalence))
- $Q = 80.46$ ($Q = 80.46$ ($100 - P$))
- $E = 5$ ($E = 5$ (allowable error))

The calculated sample size was 240.

Study Procedure

- **Sample Collection:** ETA samples were collected at intubation and 48 hours post-intubation using a sterile 22G suction catheter or Paul's ET culture bottle. Samples were obtained gently, avoiding normal saline administration, and the catheter tip containing the aspirate was placed in a sterile container.

- **Laboratory Analysis:** Samples were sent to the microbiology laboratory for fungal and bacterial culture. The VITEK®2 compact system (bioMérieux) was used for organism identification.
- **Data Collection:** Demographic details, clinical history, comorbidities, provisional and final diagnoses, and culture results were recorded.

Data Analysis

Data was entered into MS Excel and analyzed using SPSS (version 25). Descriptive statistics were presented as mean \pm SD, median, range, frequencies, and percentages. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Figure 1: Paul's ET culture container

Figure 2: ET culture aspirate taken for sampling

Figure 3: ET aspirate of patients in ICU

Results

Table 1 represents the gender distribution of study participants across different age groups. The majority of participants were in the 40-49 age group, with males outnumbering females in most categories.

Age group	Male	Female
18-29	12	5
30-39	28	10
40-49	59	34
50-59	23	19
60-69	10	16
> 70	15	11

Graph 1: Age and Gender Distribution

Table 2 represents the primary reasons for admission among study participants, with cardiac conditions being the most frequent cause (38.75%), followed by trauma/assault (14.17%). It displays the prevalence of comorbidities, with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) and hypertension (HTN) being the most common at 32.5% and 30%, respectively.

CAUSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
CARDIAC	93	38.75
TRAUMA/ASSAULT	34	14.17
POISONING	19	7.92
GASTROINTESTINAL/HEPATOBIILIARY	10	4.17
GENITOURINARY	6	2.5
CO-MORBIDITIES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
T2DM	78	32.5
HTN	72	30
HYPOTHYROIDISM	43	17.9
CKD	24	10
CLD	12	5

Graph 2: Distribution according to their cause for admission

Aetiology of Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia (Vap) in Patients Having Candida Colonization in Endotracheal Aspirate

Graph 3: Demographic distribution according to their comorbidity

Table 3 represents the distribution of VAP culture results, with 34.17% of the samples testing positive for VAP and 65.83% testing negative. The second chart illustrates the Gram stain results, revealing a predominance of negative cultures (37), followed by non-Candida organisms (34), while mixed cultures with both MRSA and Candida were relatively rare. These distributions provide insights into microbial involvement in ventilator-associated pneumonia cases.

VAP CULTURE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
POSITIVE	82	34.17
NEGATIVE	158	65.83
GRAM STAIN	FREQUENCY	
POSITIVE	11	
NEGATIVE	37	
Non-Candida	34	
Candida		
BOTH	2	
MRSA	2	
Other		

Graph 4: Distribution according to their VAP culture

Graph 5: Distribution of study subjects according to gram stain

Table 4 represents the distribution of bacterial species causing VAP among the study participants. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was the most common pathogen (10%), followed closely by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (9.16%) and *Acinetobacter baumannii* (7.03%). Other identified species included *Escherichia coli* (5.83%) and *Proteus vulgaris* (2.08%). This data highlights the predominance of gram-negative bacteria in VAP cases.

SPECIES CAUSING VAP	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
<i>PSEUDOMONAS AERUGINOSA</i>	24	10
<i>KLEBSIELLA PNEUMONIAE</i>	22	9.16
<i>ACINETOBACTER BAUMANNII</i>	17	7.03
<i>ESCHERICHIA COL</i>	14	5.83
<i>PROTEUS VULGARIS</i>	5	2.08
TOTAL	82	34.17

Graph 6: Demographic distribution of species causing VAP.

Table 5 represents the clinical outcomes of patients with VAP based on the Candida species isolated. Candida albicans showed the highest recovery rate (26 cases), followed by Candida tropicalis (13 cases). Worsening outcomes and deaths were less frequent, with only 2 deaths associated with Candida albicans and 1 with Candida tropicalis. Candida auris, although rare, showed one worsened outcome. This emphasizes the variability in patient outcomes depending on the Candida species involved.

OUTCOME	<i>CANDIDA ALBICANS</i>	<i>CANDIDA TROPICALIS</i>	<i>CANDIDA GLABRATA</i>	<i>CANDIDA AURIS</i>
RECOVERED	26	13	3	0
SAME	12	7	2	0
WORSENERD	5	3	1	1
DEATH	2	1	0	0

Graph 7: Distribution of study subject according to candida species and their outcome

Aetiology of Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia (Vap) in Patients Having Candida Colonization in Endotracheal Aspirate

Figure 4: Growth of *C. Albicans* and *C. Glabrata*

Figure 5: Growth of *Candida Tropicalis* on chrome agar
(Reproduced with the permission from Microbiology Dept. of HIMS dated 22/09/23)

Figure 6: Chrome Agar showing different species of *Candida*
 Candida differential chrom agar interpretation Chart

Candida differential chrom agar interpretation Chart

Species	Appearance on
Chrom	Agar
<i>Candida glabrata</i>	Purple
<i>Candida Tropicalis</i>	Metal Blue
<i>Candida Albicans</i>	Apple green

Discussion

Ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) is a significant clinical issue, particularly in critically ill patients requiring prolonged mechanical ventilation. This study provides valuable insights into the demographic characteristics, pathogen distribution, and diagnostic challenges associated with VAP, focusing on the role of *Candida* colonization in endotracheal aspirates.

In this study, the mean age of participants was 48.28 years (± 22.41), with a range of 18–78 years. The majority of participants (93 out of 240) were between 40 and 49 years of age. These findings are consistent with those of *Mokhless et al. [5]*, who reported a mean age of 43.1 ± 24.68 years in the VAP group. The similarity in demographics highlights the consistency of VAP incidence across studies globally.

Males represented the majority of participants (147 out of 240), mirroring the findings of *Mokhless et al.[5]*, where the male-to-female ratio was 55:45%. This male predominance likely reflects ICU admission patterns rather than a gender predisposition to VAP. Furthermore, there was no significant difference in the age distribution between male and female participants in this study.

Endotracheal aspirates were utilized for pathogen identification in this study. Although these are widely used in clinical settings due to their simplicity, the positive predictive value of such cultures is low because of contamination with non-pathogenic upper respiratory flora. To improve specificity, semi-quantitative culture methods with predefined threshold values were recommended, aiding in differentiating colonization from infection.

Candida species, particularly **Candida albicans**, were the most frequently isolated organisms, accounting for 63.3% of all isolates. Candida thrives in warm, humid ICU environments and is commonly found colonizing medical devices such as endotracheal tubes. Its ability to form biofilms and hyphae enhances its survival and colonization in critically ill patients. These findings align with global research, indicating that Candida colonization is associated with prolonged mechanical ventilation and extended ICU stays.

Among bacterial pathogens, **Pseudomonas aeruginosa** was the most common, accounting for 21.57% of isolates, followed by polymicrobial growth (19.67%) and **Staphylococcus aureus** (12.75%). This distribution is consistent with studies by *Shalaby [6]*, *Seweilam[7]*, and *Abd El-Kader[1]*, who identified Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Klebsiella pneumoniae, and Acinetobacter baumannii as the leading pathogens in VAP. The predominance of gram-negative bacteria underscores the need for targeted antimicrobial strategies.

The findings of this study align with global observations:

Mokhless et al.[5] reported similar age and gender distributions, reinforcing demographic patterns seen in VAP cases.

Hassan et al. [8], *Bachinskaya et al. [9]*, and *Apfalter et al. [10]* highlighted atypical pathogens such as **Mycoplasma pneumoniae** and **Chlamydia pneumoniae** in VAP cases, emphasizing the need for advanced diagnostic tools. Although these pathogens were not identified in the current study, their potential role should not be overlooked.

Candida albicans, the predominant fungal isolate in this study, was similarly reported as a major pathogen in other research, affirming its role as a significant colonizer in ICU settings.

Implications for Clinical Practice

The findings of this study highlight several important clinical considerations. Candida colonization in endotracheal aspirates, though not always indicative of infection, may increase the risk of secondary bacterial infections, contributing to VAP development. Antifungal strategies may be beneficial for patients with prolonged ICU stays or mechanical ventilation. Empirical antibiotic regimens for VAP should consider the local pathogen profile and include coverage for atypical organisms such as Chlamydia pneumoniae and Mycoplasma pneumoniae, as suggested by studies employing real-time PCR for rapid detection.

The high prevalence of gram-negative bacteria, particularly Pseudomonas aeruginosa, underscores the importance of antimicrobial stewardship programs to mitigate resistance and optimize patient outcomes. Localized surveillance and tailored treatment protocols are essential for addressing the specific pathogen distribution in different ICUs.

Limitations and Future Directions

One limitation of this study is the reliance on endotracheal aspirates, which have inherent diagnostic challenges. Future studies should incorporate advanced diagnostic tools like real-time PCR to detect atypical and fastidious organisms. Additionally, research should focus on the clinical outcomes of patients with *Candida* colonization and its role in VAP progression.

Conclusion

This study reinforces the complexity of VAP's etiology, with *Candida albicans* and gram-negative bacteria such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* emerging as the most common pathogens. Our study emphasizes the importance of enhanced diagnostic methods to differentiate colonization from infection, as well as the need for comprehensive empirical treatment strategies. Addressing both bacterial and fungal pathogens effectively could significantly improve outcomes for critically ill patients with VAP.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Consent: Written consent from participants has been obtained and preserved.

Ethical Approval: Ethical approval was obtained and documented as per institutional guidelines.

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Aetiology of Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia (Vap) in Patients Having Candida Colonization in Endotracheal Aspirate

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